

COMPARISON OF THREE NDT TECHNIQUES FOR THE INSPECTION OF AERONAUTIC COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

L. Scheed¹, J. Lewandowski^{1*}, M.P. Georges², R. Dubé¹, L. Mouret¹,

¹Centre Technologique en Aérospatiale, St-Hubert, Canada, ²Centre Spatial de Liège, Angleur, Belgium

* Corresponding author (jacques.lewandowski@college-em.qc.ca)

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1 Introduction

The composite aerospace industry grows continuously and the needs for reliable non-destructive testing (NDT) technologies and techniques are high. The Centre Technologique en Aérospatiale (CTA) is unique in its kind, for it gathers three major emerging inspection methods in one place: shearography, thermography and laser-ultrasonics. The interest of these methods is that these are contactless and can then be used to easily inspect complex shaped structures. In order to challenge and demonstrate their capacities, those three cutting-edge technologies were used to inspect aeronautic composite parts provided by the Centre Spatial de Liège (CSL). These parts are representative parts with complex shapes and induced defects which were manufactured by industrial partners of the CSL.

2 Inspection techniques

2.1 Shearography

Shearography is an optical method, based on speckle interferometry, for the non-contact measurement of out-of-plane deformations of a material surface [1]. Fig.1 shows the basic principle of shearography. The laser beam illuminates the object which scatters light partly to the CCD camera in front of which a device consisting of a beam splitter and two folding mirrors is arranged. This device allows separating the image in two equal images and recombining them with a lateral image shift (or shear). At the overlap of twin images, interference occurs and is recorded electronically. This operation is achieved during variation of the object, e.g. when the latter is heated by a lamp. These patterns are then subtracted electronically to reveal the derivative of the surface displacement field caused by a defect underneath the surface. Shearography inspection of composite parts was performed using a Dantec Q800 apparatus,

equipped with eight lasers of 120mW at a wavelength of 660nm and monitored by ISTR44D X86 software. Thermal load can be applied by a heating lamp of 750W. This apparatus is mobile and can be fixed on a robot for scanning large parts. Fig.2 shows the typical setup used in our facilities.

2.2 Thermography

Pulsed thermography is one of the most popular method in active thermography [2]. One reason for this is the quickness of the inspection and the relatively wide field of view. Pulsed thermography uses a short thermal stimulation, where the flash light duration goes from a few milliseconds for high conductivity materials (such as metal) to a few seconds for low conductivity ones (such as plastics). In addition, the brief heating sequence prevents damage to the component (see Fig.3). In our laboratory, the object receives an optical flash of 3 kJ during 10 ms, and an IR Telops camera (3,5 to 5 μ m) records the temperature evolution for each pixel of the 640 x 512 detector area. The surface temperature evolution may be different for a defect free area and a defect location (see Fig.4).

Many processing techniques are then available [3] in order to determine the dimension and depth of the defect. Two processing techniques were used: Principal Component Thermography (PCT) and Fast Fourier transform (FFT) showing either the amplitude or phase image (PPT).

2.3 Laser-ultrasonics

Ever since its first proof of concept on aeronautic materials in 1998 [4], the laser-ultrasonics made a major step forward in automation. A pulsed CO₂ laser beam is focussed on the object surface, and generates the ultrasound wave inside the material,

without any couplant (see Fig.5), though the thermoelastic effect which does not degrade the surface material. The surface movement induced by the ultrasound wave is detected by an interferometer using a long laser pulse from a YAG laser (1064 nm) and either a Fabry-Perot interferometer for measuring measuring Doppler shift of the local surface or Two Wave Mixing [5] for small displacements created by the ultrasound echoes (see Fig.6), as is the case with our system.

From a practical point of view, a Laser Ultrasonics Inspection System (LUIS, Tecnar©) (Fig.7) has been robotised to create a complete NDT solution for aerospace complex geometry composite parts. It uses a pulsed 100 mJ CO₂ generation laser with a pulsed 20 mJ YAG detection laser at a frequency of 100 Hz. The spot diameter is 3mm and can run at any defined user's speed (in our case, a speed of 50 mm/s with a 2.5mm overlap).

3 Inspected parts

Four main aeronautic types of geometry made of CRFP were inspected by thermography, shearography and the laser-ultrasonics. Each part presents a complex 3D shape (omega insertion, curvature, stiffener(s), etc.) with artificial defects included during manufacturing (voids, PTFE insertions, etc.).

3.1 Plate with an omega shape

A 30x30 cm² carbon-epoxy plate with an omega-shape stiffener in the middle was analyzed (see Fig. 8): 42 defects were included through variable depths (voids and insertions).

3.2 Wing leading edge

A portion of a carbon-epoxy wing leading edge (50cm long and 20cm wide) with a U-shape and a stiffener in the inner side was analyzed (see Fig. 9). Ten included defects had to be localised through variable depths. The nature of the defects was unknown.

3.3 Section of a stator ring

A section of a circular carbon-epoxy part with a 50cm radius of curvature, 40cm long and 15cm wide was analyzed (see Fig.10). A thin glass coating is deposited on that part. A hundred defects (PTFE, resin and steel inserts) were included at three different depths.

3.4 Panel with integrated stiffeners

A 125 x 100 cm² in panel with several stiffeners and two spars was analyzed (shown in Fig. 7): 32 defects were included through variable thicknesses (PTFE insertions of different sizes and geometries)

4 NDT parameters and results

4.1 Shearography

The goal of shearography is to detect quickly different kinds of defects located at different depths on different types of aeronautical parts. No defect dimensioning or depth location will be done. Parts were tested into many zones in order to detect all the inserted calibrated defects. The area analysed was about 30 x 30 cm². The shear factor was set at a value of 6 mm and the shear angle at 70°. In some cases, parts were covered with dye penetrant developer in order to enhance the reflectivity of the surface. Also, some surfaces are very reflective and saturate the image giving a non-uniform shearogram [6].

4.1.1 Plate with an omega shape

The shearogram of that part (Fig. 11) shows that detected defects located under the first CFRP laminate ply (maximum depth of 0.2 mm) are detected whatever their size. Some of them are detected under the second CFRP ply. Rectangular indications are inserted materials and small round indication are simulating voids made of two layers of PTFE. All void defects located under the first laminate ply are detected and some under the second one. Some inserted defects are not detected under the first laminate ply. For example, the release film insertion was never detected. Another mean of excitation, like vacuum or acoustic excitation, may reveal it. However, an inserted flash breaker film can be detected at a depth up to 1.4 mm. The mechanical properties of the defect and the bond between the defect and the surrounding material have strong effect on the shearogram [6]. From all the 42 defects, shearography allowed the detection of 17.

4.1.2 Wing leading edge

Fig. 12 shows the shearogram for the wing leading edge. Inserted defects are unknown except for

laminate plies junctions and their location. The defects located under the first CFRP laminate ply are well detected and the ply junctions as well. However, in that case, only the contour defect is visible on shearogram. If the defect has a strong bond with the surrounding material, nothing could be detected. Another excitation can be useful in that case. However, the underneath stiffener of the part is clearly visible on shearogram (Fig. 12). For this object, shearography detected 8 out of the 10 known defects.

4.1.3 Section of a stator ring

Like other parts, PTFE and steel defects located under the first glass ply (0.6mm) are visible on the shearogram, whatever their size (Fig. 13). However, the defects of DY5054 (20 X 20 mm²) are not visible despite their large size. The nature of that defect does not affect the deformation during the heat and thus the shearogram during test. Another excitation mode would be useful to detect this defect. The curved geometry of that section was not a problem for detection of defect but dye penetrant has been applied to avoid parasite reflections on the shearogram. In this case, 33 defects were found from the 100 known defects. To reveal the maximum number of defects, both sides of that part have been analyzed, convex and concave sides. In a real industrial situation, only the convex side inspection would be done, thus decreasing the detected number of defects.

4.1.4 Panel with integrated stiffeners

This part has an added difficulty in terms of inspection because of its complex geometry which is an assembly of many elementary parts. It is not easy to get a uniform reference shearogram on the object surface without parasite reflections coming from surrounding surfaces with different orientations (Fig. 14). When it was possible, PTFE defects were detected under the first laminate ply (0.6mm) but sometimes in the middle ply of about 1.5mm (Fig. 15). That Fig. also shows underneath structure like stiffeners. It is important to set the shear angle across the underneath beam direction to be able to properly detect it. Also, if the defect is located between two different assembly parts, the defect cannot be seen entirely on the shearogram. Fig. 15 shows a defect located at the junction between a

stiffener and the main plate where the defect can be hardly seen in the corner.

4.2 Thermography

Active pulse thermography was applied to the four objects and two signal processing techniques (FFT and PCT) were applied to enhance the defects visibility. The observed area was approximately 20 x 20 cm², each video sequence was recorded during 60 s at a rate of 25 fps. The processing time for either FFT or PCT took approximately 2 to 3 minutes.

Fig. 16 shows the result for the omega shape plate. The amplitude image of the FFT is shown. Detection of an unexpected defect is obvious on this image. Only the subsurface defects were detected with this technique, deep ones do not appear on the image.

Fig. 17 shows the section of the stator ring analyzed using amplitude of the FFT and PCT. Steel, resin and teflon inserts are clearly detected in both images. These defects are located close to the surface. Both signal processing techniques give identical results in this case.

Fig. 18 shows the results on the panel with integrated stiffeners using PCT with different correlation coefficients. Defects located 1,5 mm under the surface are detected with this method.

4.3 Laser ultrasonics

Ultrasounds generated by laser impact were revealed as the most accurate and reliable technique. The integration of the LUIS probe to a robot gave unprecedented results on complex geometries. Fig. 19 shows an example of results obtained with the LUIS on the omega plate.

Fig. 20 shows the results on the wind leading edge surface. Clearly, these results show the advantage of laser ultrasonics for the detection of deep defects in composite materials. Also, one can see the image is clearly defined and not blurred as for thermography or shearography.

Results obtained with the stator section were not very accurate (see Fig.21) because the thin glass coating prevented from having a good ultrasonic signal.

Finally, Fig. 22 shows the potential of laser ultrasonics with a C-scan and a 3D representation of the object and defect superimposed.

5. Comparison and Conclusion

Shearography is well suitable for CFRP panels where the inspection can be done quickly for defects lying under the first laminate plies.

Voids as small as 4 mm can be detected under the first laminate ply. Larger void size can be detected at depths up to 2 mm.

Defect of foreign materials added during manufacturing can be detected: the result depends on the depth in the part thickness, their bond capabilities with the surrounding CRFP, and also their mechanical properties.

Defect located in corners are difficult to detect because of reflection coming from surrounding surfaces of added components.

Thermography allowed detection of the inserts that are not too deep (depth ≤ 2 mm) in those high performance composite parts. Identification of the defect is more difficult: determination of the defect type and depth demands careful signal processing and analysis. Comparison of PCT and PPT techniques was performed successfully. The test results are comparable to those obtained by shearography. Both these field methods are quite complementary. Shearography is a bit simpler to set-up but the results are difficult to interpret in term of defect depth. Thermography is a bit more expensive (if one wishes to use high end cooled camera), however the post processing possibilities are more advanced than with shearography. When material properties are well known, the depth could be estimated but this still requires numerous methodology efforts. Nevertheless it is known that thermal diffusion quickly degrades the thermal contrast, preventing detecting deep defects, whereas one can hope mechanical reaction still visible by shearography for those defects.

Laser ultrasonics was the most efficient technique and allowed detection of most defects, combining better depth penetration and precision. Nevertheless the system is more complex, more expensive than both other methods and it requires scanning.

Our global conclusion is that these methods are truly complementary for inspecting complex shaped structures, with full-field methods giving quicker

answer of shallow defects localization, whereas laser ultrasound allows detecting deeper defects, with determination of depth.

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Comparison of three NDT techniques for the inspection of aeronautic composite structures

Fig. 1- Principle of a shearographic system with heating sample stimulation

Fig. 2 – Dantec shearographic system

Fig. 3 - Principle of active pulse thermography

Fig. 4 - Thermograms of an object in pulse thermography: T_s is defect free and T_d is with defect

Fig. 5 – Laser ultrasound generation by thermoelastic effect

Fig. 6 – Surface detection with a single frequency laser (YAG) and the Two Wave Mixing in a photorefractive crystal.

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Fig. 7 - LUIS (Laser Ultrasound Inspection System) on a robot, showing the panel with integrated stiffeners.

Fig. 8 – Omega shape plate

Fig. 9 – Wing leading edge (with the LUIS)

Fig. 10 – Stator section (thermographic set-up)

Fig. 11 – Shearogram of the omega plate

Fig. 12 - Shearogram of the wing leading edge

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Fig. 13- Shearogram of the stator section.

Fig. 14 - Shearogram of a spar belonging to panel with defects A, B, C, and underneath indication of integrated stiffeners.

Fig. 15 - Shearogram with detected defect where a underneath stiffener (horizontally indication) and ply junction can be seen (vertically indication)

Fig. 16 - Thermographic analysis on the omega shape plate using Fourier Transform (amplitude of the FFT)

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Fig. 17 - Thermography of the stator section.
Left: amplitude of the FFT. Right : PCT

Fig. 18 - Thermographic analysis of the panel with integrated stiffeners using PCT
Defect A: diameter 6 mm, depth 0.6mm
Defect B: diameter 10 mm, depth 0.6mm
Defect C: diameter 10 mm, depth 1.5mm

Fig. 19- LUIS on the omega plate

Fig. 20 – LUIS applied to the wind leading edge

Fig. 21- LUIS on the stator section

Fig. 22 – 3D representation from the LUIS data showing a defect in the stringer as well as various depths of material (color coded)